

Modern Academic Publication System- A Bitcoin-Mining Model

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Compliance Statement

Draft paper has been checked ok for compliance with working paper publication rules, copyright law and fair use rules. The subject matter is academic publication and mechanism design and applied game theory.

Abstract

This paper considers the questions- why do the current generation of academics publish papers, why do they do background research, and why do they cite reference papers from other academics, and their own back catalogue? And why do they judge peers on publications and citation rankings? The suggested answer is that when an academic creates a paper that is published in journal X or Y, then they are creating and acquiring a valuable new intangible asset like a bitcoin in cryptocurrency X or Y, that can then be converted via various direct and indirect exchanges into real legal tender academic payment flows, and other valuable tangible and intangible assets such as paid academic posts, opportunities and reputation. The proposed system that emerges is a merry-go-round including:

¹ Dr Rupert Macey-Dare LLM, see: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/cf_dev/AbsByAuth.cfm?per_id=732884 and <https://www.linkedin.com/in/rupertmacedare/> . Draft paper subject to correction, review and revision. All comments and communication on this and other matters and cases gratefully received.

N.B. This paper is independent academic research and comment of the author and does not constitute and should not be read as specific advice. Any calculations and examples are indicative and illustrative only.

***** 100% AI-free paper ***, *** Single author, no RA work *****

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academics, journals, publishers, research projects, funders, libraries, students, universities and research institutes, and although highly inefficient and wasteful when compared with a perfect world alternative as a way of producing and disseminating new knowledge, it is nevertheless highly stable and robust due to the vested interests of the majority of already well-established and well-invested members of the system, who want to keep it propped up³. The proposed model can also explain the apparent paradox of academics going to huge lengths and expense to publish their work in academic journals which are actually firewalled and exclude most potential readers, when the alternative of free, global publication and knowledge distribution is, with modern technology also available. It can also help explain the phenomena of multi-authorship and hyper-authorship and paper-milling of nonsensical papers with zero or negative content value, but positive bitcoin type arbitrage value for the authors.

³ This in turn can create entry barriers for any authors trying to publish work critical of the fundamentals of the current academic publication system, since any journal editors or platform gatekeepers are very likely to be highly published academics, naturally uncomfortable with and resistant to what could be perceived as a challenge to the basis of their own academic status.

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A simple illustrative model

The diagram above shows a simple model of an academic ecosystem where academic publications are produced, are valued and valuable and help drive different flows around the model.⁴

The model includes different schematic blocks of different actors, connected by arrows representing different directed flows of assets or money in a graph, flowing between different blocks.

Occasionally arrows between blocks are 2 way. There can be a number of arrows between pairs of blocks and each block is typically connected by arrows to one or more blocks.

Ultimately there are directed paths along the arrows that connect almost all the blocks together and a general circular flow between all the blocks. This represents a relatively stable setup where flows of assets and money circle round the system over different time periods, such as an academic year and periods of years and decades.

Model Diagram Main Component Blocks- Key

- 1. Typical Academic Co-Author Team
- 2. Theoretical + Conceptual Universe (available to study)
- 3. Empirical + Data Universe (available to study)
- 4. Academic Publishers
- 4a. Academic Publisher Staff + Shareholders
- 5. Other Services (provided by external providers to publishers)
- 6. Reviewers/ Referees
- 7. Other Academic Teams (of different co-authors)
- 8. General Public + Other Readers (of academic journal publications)
- 9. Academic Libraries
- 10. Students (typically at universities)

⁴ For an earlier, independent stock-flow model of academic publishing, with special reference to Austrian social sciences, see: Puehringer S, Rath J, Griesebner T (2021) The political economy of academic publishing: On the commodification of a public good. PLoS ONE 16(6): e0253226. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0253226> and its references.

- 11. University
- 12. Academic Funders
- 13 Government

Model Diagram Types of Flow- Key

The main flows connecting blocks in the diagrammatic model are as follows:

Key to diagram flows

Note that the flows in the pink block above are all of notional intangible assets. What this paper will argue is that the academic formal publication process is akin to the mining of crypto-currency like Bitcoin, which can in turn be converted/ transmuted into standard currency flows such as \$ or £ in the pockets of academic authors/ co-authors, and this circular payment mechanism helps to rationalize and explain the

current academic publication system including a number of peculiar and at 1st glance counter-intuitive aspects.⁵

The full model is illustrated in the Diagram above, but we now discuss the key component blocks and their main linkages to other blocks. N.B. This model is highly stylized and so needs to be changed mutatis mutandis for the real world. However the intention and objective to help explore and articulate major features and drivers of the prevailing current system.

Block 1- Typical academic co-author team

Block 1 shows a typical academic co-author team and there are assumed to be multiple other similar teams in the system (not illustrated for diagrammatic clarity, but understood to be there)⁶.

Each team includes one or more authors, all connected to each other by interacting workflows that may be greater than or equal to zero.

For interactions between Block 1 and other blocks, see below.

Block 2- Theoretical and conceptual universe and Block 3- Empirical and data universe

In reality Blocks 2,3 will have some overlap, but are shown as separate for ease of illustration. These represent the conceptual and experimental data worlds respectively .

A typical academic co-author team in Block 1 will put in some work, looking at Blocks 2,3, represented diagrammatically as the directed black arrows of work input and in

⁵ This analysis applies to representative average, median academic teams and academic work production. It does not apply to world leading, top end, say Nobel Prize or Fields Medal quality research, which by definition have multiple non-representative features including exceptional quality and rarity.

This analysis also does not apply to the academic monograph books, although there will be some applicability, mutatis mutandis, to book edited collections of papers from multiple co-authors with supervising author editors.

⁶ In reality there will be millions of such teams, mutating slightly over time and with different overlaps between different teams.

return will extract research output flows of derived information, represented diagrammatically by the directed blue arrows.

Block 4- Academic publishers

Block 4 represents academic publishers. The typical academic co-author team in block 1 contributes research output (the blue directed arrow) and also direct work (the black arrow) to the academic publisher. In return, the typical academic co-author team in block 1 receives academic publication credits (the gold dashed arrow) from the academic publisher⁷. In other words, academic co-authors of articles for journal X will typically flag this valuable, differentiating, intangible asset information on their c.v. and university profiles.

There can also be instances where Block 1- typical academic co-author team pays money to the academic publisher (shown by green directed arrow) typically in return for free, open-access publication. This money payment effectively provides some financial compensation to the Block4-Academic publishers for the lost opportunity to gain money income from readers for sales of the relevant journal article. The benefit of this approach to the authors who do this is gaining broader readership of their journal article, whose marginal financial reading cost becomes zero. It may also

⁷ The ubiquity of this arrangement in academic publishing can blind by familiarity the viewer from realizing just how strange this is at 1st glance. In almost all commercial publishing, the publisher pays the authors in real cash, say £ or \$ for their work and publishers and authors share the value generated according to some bargaining scheme and agreement.

In very uncommon, non-commercial, vanity publishing, the authors may pay the publishers to publish their work, because there is high publication demand from these authors and no commercial demand from readers.

By contrast, in most academic publishing there are zero financial returns from the publisher to the authors and the publisher keeps all the financial returns, which are substantial.

There are also a number of academic publications including open access, where the academics actually “pay-to-play” and pay the publishers to publish.

But academic authors by definition are not systematically stupid over time, so they would not be throwing away time, effort and sometimes money as well for no return. So the academics must be getting something valuable in return and what is it? This is the question considered and explored in detail in this paper below.

potentially be easier for such articles to be accepted as the publisher has greater upfront incentive to accept the draft article as is⁸.

For interactions between Block 4 and other blocks, see below.

Block 4a- Academic publisher staff + shareholders

Block 4a represents Academic publisher staff + shareholders. This is connected to Block 4- Academic publishers in 2 ways. Firstly there is an outflow of work (black directed arrow) and ownership effect (not shown) from the Block 4a- Academic publisher staff + shareholders to the Block 4- Academic publishers. Secondly there is an inflow of money from the Block 4- Academic publishers to the Block 4a Academic publisher staff + shareholders and this is a main way that actual money flows are extracted from the whole system⁹ to people connected with actual publication rather than authorship.

Block 5- Other services

The academic publishers in Block 4 are connected to Block 5-Other services in 2 ways. Firstly there is an inflow of work (the black directed arrow) from Block 5-Other services to Block 4- Academic publishers and secondly a corresponding outflow of real money for those services (the green directed arrow). So these arrows represent standard contractual services provided by Block 5 to the Block 4-Academic publishers.

⁸ The presence of alternative but comparable open access academic journals where the academic authors are charged to publish is discussed below as part of a potential empirical modelling experiment to estimate implied financial values to academics of publishing in standard non-open access journals and is one potential way that these shadow financial values could be calculated.

Implementing this experiment is left as an exercise for further work or other authors.

⁹ A common complaint is that academic publishers, but in fact flowing through to their staff and shareholders, generate huge and excess profits from their journals, to the detriment of academic authors, and academic readers and knowledge distribution and production.

Block 6- Reviewers & Referees

Block 6- Reviewers & Referees can be connected in multiple ways with Block 4- Academic publishers. The research drafts (blue arrow) flow initially and primarily from the Block 4-Academic publishers to the Block 6- Reviewers & Referees. But there may also be a back-flow the other way, if the reviewers and referees require corrections or changes, in which case there is a further backflow from Block 4- Academic publishers back to Block 1- the relevant academic co-author team. This potential backflow is in fact critically important, because it provides the theoretical peer review “added value” and quality control of formal peer review publication¹⁰.

The Block 6- Reviewers & Referees provide work (the directed black arrow) for the Block 4-Academic publishers. The Block 6- Reviewers & Referees may also receive some money (the directed green arrow) from the Block 4-Academic publishers, although generally not and this is a major source of complaint (about effective exploitation) made by the academic referees and reviewers. And the Block 6- Reviewers & Referees typically also receive reviewer credits (the directed dashed dark red arrow) from the Block 4-Academic publishers. In other words, academic reviewers for journal X will typically flag this valuable, differentiating, intangible asset information on their c.v. profiles. For additional interactions between Block 6 and other blocks, see below.¹¹

Block 8- General Public & Other Students & Readers

For our purposes Block 8- General Public & Other Students & Readers is connected to Block 4-Academic publishers in 2 ways. Firstly Block 8- General Public & Other Students & Readers pays money (the green directed arrow) to Block 4-Academic publishers and in return receives final publication distribution of academic journal

¹⁰ It is of course a moot point whether or not this adds any positive or negative value at all overall and in any particular cases.

¹¹ Presumably there is also a large population or sub-population of conscientious commercial academic journal editors, probably motivated by public benefits considerations and intrinsic rewards. However there is also another subsection famously complained about by academic article submitters, who appear to be motivated by power and control and the chance to say No.

publications. Block 8- General Public & Other Students & Readers thereby provide one of the main input sources of regular money flows into the whole system¹².

¹² If one assumes that quasi-monopoly prices are charged, then money inflows can be almost maximized but at the implicit cost of restricting information access to readers who value the journal article information, but at less than the sale price.

Block 9- Academic Libraries

Block 9- Academic Libraries is linked to Block 4-Academic publishers in 2 ways. Firstly Block 9- Academic Libraries pays money (the green directed arrow) to Block 4-Academic publishers and in return receives final publication distribution of academic journal publications (shown as a blue dashed arrow).

Block 9- Academic Libraries then passes the academic journal information (shown as a blue dashed arrow) typically for free to Block-10 students. And Block 9- Academic Libraries in turn receives money flows needed to pay the Block 4-Academic publishers (shown as green directed input arrow) from Block 11-University.

Block 10- Students

Block 10-Students receive funding (all shown as green input arrows) from Block-13 Government in some circumstances and from Block-14 Other Student Funders and from their own external work and savings. These are fundamental money inputs into the broader system.

Block 10-Students then pay out fees (shown as a green output arrow) to Block 11- University (or similar institution) and in return receive academic education credits (shown as the gold dotted arrow) which can become very valuable intangible assets for the students in the form of degrees and recognised qualifications that are remunerated in the workplace.

There is also a 2 way flow of work (shown as a bidirectional black arrow) between Block 10-Students and Block 1- Academics, e.g. attending lectures and writing essays from Block 10-Students and delivering lectures and marking essays and exams from Block 1- Academics. There is also a 2 way flow of good reputation (shown as a bidirectional dotted red arrow) between Block 10-Students and Block 1- Academics as each group typically needs the other to maintain a good reputation in that environment.

Block 13- Government

Block 13- Government includes both local and centralized government funding and services. In addition to some funding (shown as green arrows) of Block 10-Students, Block 13- Government also provides funding to Block 11- University and Block 12- Academic Funders, including funding bodies. There is also a 2-way flow of work (shown as bidirectional black arrows) between Block 13- Government and Block 11- University and between Block 13- Government and Block 12- Academic Funders.

Block 12- Academic Funders

Block 12-Academic Funders raise funds (shown as green arrows) on their own and from Block 13- Government.

Block 12-Academic Funders then pay out funds (shown as green arrows) to Block-11 University and there is a mutual good reputation flow (shown as a bidirectional red dotted arrow) between Block 12-Academic Funders and Block-11 University.

Block-12 Academic Funders also pay out funds (shown as green arrows) to Block 1- Typical Academic Co-Author Teams. In return Block-12 Academic Funders receive a number of intangible asset flows back from Block 1- Typical Academic Co-Author Teams including: academic publication credits (shown as a gold dashed line) and academic citation credits (shown as a red dashed line) and good reputation and publicity (shown as a red dotted line).

Block 11- University

Block 11-University interacts with Block 1- Typical Academic Co-Author Teams in a number of ways. Firstly, assuming an employment type relationship¹³ there is a 2-way flow of work (shown as a bidirectional black line) between the 2 blocks.

¹³ This section is a simplification of the real world where a single co-author group can have members who are employees of different universities, so needs to be generalized for the real world mutatis mutandis.

Secondly there will typically be a flow of funds (shown as a green arrow) from: Block 11-University to Block 1- Typical Academic Co-Author Team.

In return Block-11 University also receive a number of intangible asset flows back from Block 1- Typical Academic Co-Author Teams including: academic publication credits (shown as a gold dashed line) and academic citation credits (shown as a red dashed line) and good reputation and publicity (shown as a red dotted line).

Block-11 University will also typically make payments (shown as green arrows) out to Block 9- Academic Libraries, to pay for library staff and upkeep and publication subscriptions.

Block 11 University will also typically make payments (shown as green arrows) out to Block 6- Referees/ Reviewers inasmuch as they are its employees and will in turn receive back Academic Reviewer credits (shown as a maroon arrow).

[Block-7 Other Academic Teams](#)

Block 1- Typical Academic Co-Author Team under main consideration will also be connected to any number of similar teams such as Block-7 Other Academic Teams, which in turn have a similar web of links.

In particular each Block 1- Typical Academic Co-Author Team and Block-7 Other Academic Team will be connected by a 2-way flow of academic citation credits (shown as bidirectional red dashed arrows) and also good reputation credits (shown as bidirectional red dotted arrows).

[Asset creation and asset flows in the academic publication process](#)

If we look back at the Diagram Flows- Key above, and at the network diagram above, it can now be seen that the modern academic publication process, typically by university academic author teams, set in a university and academic publishing context involves the production of new publications based on new intellectual

analysis and discovery, the distribution of this information in a partly restricted way, and flows of money payments to and from participants in this web.

Block 1- Typical Academic Co-Author Team will typically receive employment income, based in large part on their production of academic publications and academic reputation based on both publications and citations received. There is a broad exchange rate between an academics stock and production of new publications and associated good reputation and citations (all valuable intangible assets) and their employment income. As such the production of new publications and associated good reputation and citations by an academic can be seen as the mining of intangible assets that can be exchanged for monetary value, akin to cryptocurrency such as Bitcoin mining. Just as Bitcoin mining can be seen as a technically robust but highly inefficient process in terms of energy in and value out, the same objection can also be levelled at the modern academic publication system. And just as individual Bitcoin miners may work to pool resources to maximize efficiency and generate for free valuable resources where possible, so Academic Co-Author Teams may do the same in optimizing team size and composition and the outflow and inflow of valuable citations.

According to this model and analysis, the modern academic publication production system is highly rational albeit also highly inefficient because it is driven by economic competition for career success and progression. It is also likely to be highly stable, until eventually swept aside by new technology. That is because new recruits who might reasonably question the current system are in a distinct minority of less than 10%¹⁴. The remaining 90% of incumbents are those who already have a good stack of official academic publications and citation intangible assets, from which they can

¹⁴ Suppose for example average academic careers are 30y long and the system size is stable. Then about $1/30 = 3.3\%$ academics will complete their careers per year providing new spots for 3.3% of the academic pool- all evaluated by incumbent academics using their chosen academic publication centric metrics.

Suppose additionally that the academic workforce is growing at 5% p.a, a relatively high growth rate. Then that will still equate to less than 10% new academics per year, being evaluated by existing academics in the same way, giving existing evaluation methodologies very high inertia and sustainability.

N.B. There is also an underlying behavioural trait, observed in many domains of life, that any individual evaluator A will tend to evaluate individual evaluatees B,C,D, using a yardstick that self-evaluates A most highly, providing homophilic high evaluation and preferred selection and so selection bias.

extract a type of monopoly employment rent and so are highly unlikely to be persuaded to change a system that already values them (obviously correctly in their view) so highly already.

Estimating the financial value of academic publications to academic authors

We know that academic publications are valuable to academic journal publishers because we can in principle review their financial accounts, profitability and share prices. We can also review individual article and journal and subscription costs to ultimate consumers.

But this leaves open the question of where in the production chain is financial value created. Is it just at the publication stage or, as argued above, at the academic author creation stage, albeit that academics may then be paid initially in valuable intangible assets akin to an implicit cryptocurrency?

One way we can estimate this is by comparing open access academic journals, where the authors typically have to pay for publication v comparable pay per view academic journals where authors typically can submit for free.

Suppose we take a number of observations of matched pairs of open access journals v pay per view, where each pair is otherwise comparable i.e. of similar subject coverage and quality and impact factor.

Then regression type analysis should allow estimation of the financial value to author-groups both of the expected extra downloads and reads from open access publication v paid only access, and also the financial value of publication per se of an article in a journal with a specific quality and impact factor.

Example and discussion:

- Journal type A, impact factor X, open access cost to authors \$10k, expected open access downloads 20k, expected paid downloads equivalent 15k
- Then, assuming linearity and rationality, then the expected minimum value to the authors of the baseline pay per view publication in Journal type A, impact factor X = $\$10k * 15k / (20k - 15k) = \$10k * 3 = \$30k$.
- Repeat this analysis for matched pairs of comparable academic publication journals A_i , with comparable impact factors X_i , to estimate the implicit value across the whole market of different academic publications in journals with different characteristics and impact factors.
-
- Suppose additionally that an academic article costs \$C to produce, based on the shadow cost of the authors research time.
- Suppose that the number of co-authors is N, then the average shadow cost ASC of article production per co-author is $\$C/N$.
- Clearly ASC falls as number of co-authors N rises.
- Now if there is effectively double-counting and each co-author is attributed similar credit for multi-author work as for single author work, and if that credit can be converted into financial value as outlined above then this provides a clear financial incentive for academic authors to produce large numbers of papers in large co-author groups, rather than small numbers of single author papers taking exactly the same amount of total time.
- Additionally the use of larger co-author groups will allow some co-authors to manipulate the rest of the group and contribute close to \$0 input cost, as discussed in other papers.
-

What sort of crypto-currencies are academic publications?

A normal cryptocurrency such as Bitcoin has a value that fluctuates over time and can be traded and converted at a locked-in exchange rate at any specific different transaction time and date when exchanged for say \$ or £ cash. Other comparable

cryptocurrencies will behave similarly but exhibiting different exchange rate paths for conversion into say \$ or £ cash.

As argued above, academic publications can be viewed as a form of crypto-currency and the academic journal production by academics as a form of bitcoin mining, because it creates new intangible assets- here academic publication assets, that can be converted through a complex swaps type process indicatively illustrated in the Diagram, into real financial cash return for the academic authors.

However there are some major differences also that are worth exploring. Firstly formal cryptocurrencies which are not backed up by real assets tend to be hugely volatile, whereas the value of say a Nature or Science or Cell publication for an academic author is agreed to be very high and also relatively stable. This might suggest that a better analogy is between academic publications and asset-backed crypto-currencies such as stablecoins. That would imply that the value of a top academic journal publication was seen as backed up by the valuable intangible underlying asset of the associated valuable knowledge production and attribution and also the high brand value of the publication.

A second difference is that whereas an amount of cryptocurrency can be sold once only for cash, a top academic journal publication on an academic's c.v. can help fill many career years of salary and earnings and so is more like an annuity or bond holding for the relevant author. However this apparent difference is easily accommodated by realizing that there is typically an equilibrium exchange fair value between an annuity or bond holding and cash lump sum, and indeed this is the basis under which these products are typically sold by providers to consumers.

[Note on diagrammatic analysis above](#)

The diagrammatic analysis of the proposed system combines elements from all of the following:

- Network diagrams
- Stock flow diagrams
- Production diagrams

- Decision making diagrams
- Knowledge production diagrams

This is because the proposed system includes all these elements (and additionally random network links, and reduplication and generalization, not illustrated for clarity)

Note on current methodology for attribution of citation counts and academic impact factors

Interestingly academic impact factors are typically based on citation records but these are not all citations but ONLY citations from journals within the commercial academic publishing ecosystem. What this means is that this prevalent methodology pushed and supported by the commercial academic publishing ecosystem actually rewards and locks academic authors into using it only, and thus introduces a huge bias in favour of academic authors using traditional commercial academic publishing to the exclusion and disfavour of other competitors. In other words there seems to have been something like regulatory capture of the prevalent academic ranking system by and for the benefit of the commercial academic publishing ecosystem.

This can lead to the bizarre results and comparative rankings, illustrated by this example. Suppose that there are two comparable academic authors A and B. Suppose that author A publishes 3 commercial academic papers as part of a 10 man co-author group for each paper which each paper receives 1 download each and 5 citations to other paid academic journals. Suppose by contrast that author B publishes 20 academic working papers as a single author each with 1000 downloads each and 50 citations to other open working papers. In this pairwise comparison example author A is highly regarded and rewarded in official metrics as having 3 publications and 15 citations and a high impact factor. Author B is regarded as having 0 publications and 0 citations and 0 impact, when looking only at commercial academic publications.

However if one were looking at working papers as well, then B would have 20 publications and 1000 citations and a very high impact factor.

And if one were looking at Single Author Equivalent SAE measures, then B's relative performance would appear even worse with only 1/3 paper and 1.5 citations on an SAE basis.

Note on publication attempts for this working paper

The 1st and unsuccessful attempt to publish this working paper was on the SSRN network, which in 2016 was brought up by and became affiliated with the Elsevier global academic publishing ecosystem¹⁵. The paper was summarily rejected at the preliminary loading review stage. No detailed explanation was given, but a link to the publishing integrity facts page provided and reproduced below¹⁶.

The 2nd unsuccessful attempt to publish this working paper was on the OCF system for the socArXiv platform. The working paper was summarily rejected for multiple reasons including that it was a "computer science paper" and "outside the scope" of socArXiv and informally that they "had to exclude AI slop". Conspicuously none of these objections could apply to this particular paper, but the broader message and hint was taken, and so it was withdrawn accordingly.

The 3rd and successful final attempt to publish this working paper was on the European Zenodo open access platform on 5 November 2025¹⁷. One week later on 12 November 2025 and despite no paper distribution, the Abstract had been viewed 124* and downloaded 100*- i.e. an initial download conversion ratio of c.81% and a promising expected annual download rate.

¹⁵ See e.g. Schonfeld R: "Elsevier Acquires SSRN" SSP Society for Scholarly Publishing Blog 17 May 2016 at <https://scholarlykitchen.sspnet.org/2016/05/17/elsevier-acquires-ssrn/>

¹⁶ Provisions of this SSRN code that might have been activated include: "Response to an increasing concern and threat from individuals that attempt to undermine the scholarly communication landscape. These checks help us to maintain trust and confidence in our content" and "editorial reasons" and "untrue authorship claims" and "suspicious papers" (sic).

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¹⁷ See Wikipedia: "Zenodo" (2025) at <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Zenodo>

Evolution of the modern academic publication system + future prospects?

The Modern Academic Publication system analysed and discussed in this paper has certainly existed and been developing in the current form over the last 30 years, since the ubiquity of the internet and World Wide Web and the advent of pdf publication files and online journals.

The Bitcoin analogy is only strictly available from 2008 and the publication of the original Bitcoin cryptocurrency proposal¹⁸ by a pseudonymous and still unmasked “Satoshi Nakamoto”¹⁹. However valuable intangible assets and rights have been recognized in legal systems such as English Law and religions such as Christianity and cultures such as ancient Greece and Rome for thousands of years, and the value of reputation and standing in ancient cultures probably going back much further.

Before the prevalence of electronic articles there was a quite similar if much smaller and slower moving and less productive, system of academic journal publication certainly from at least the Victorian era, and in these cases the word “publication” was literally accurate because this was typically the best and only way to get new academic ideas publicized and distributed globally across academic.

Printed academic journals can be traced back certainly to the 17thC French Journal des Scavans²⁰ and the English Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society (of

¹⁸ See Satoshi Nakamoto: “Bitcoin: A Peer-to-Peer Electronic Cash System” 2008 at <https://bitcoin.org/bitcoin.pdf> and

Satoshi Nakamoto: “Bitcoin: A Peer-to-Peer Electronic Cash System” Cryptography Mailing List 31 October 2008 at <https://archive.ph/20121228025845/http://article.gmane.org/gmane.comp.encryption.general/12588/> and

Wikipedia: “Bitcoin” (2025) at <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bitcoin>

¹⁹ See e.g. Wikipedia: “Satoshi Nakamoto” (2025) at https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Satoshi_Nakamoto and

Crypto Open Patent Alliance v Wright [2024] EWHC 3315 (Ch) (19 December 2024) at <https://www.bailii.org/ew/cases/EWHC/Ch/2024/3315.pdf>

²⁰ See Wikipedia: “Journal des Scavans” (2025) at https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Journal_des_s%C3%A7avans

London)²¹. And scientific and alchemical treatises back certainly to ancient Greece and Aristotle²² and perhaps earlier. So the modern academic publishing system can be seen as the culmination and flowering of a long evolutionary process, with significant changes along the way.

This leads to the question of whether the current modern academic publication system is now stable or likely to change again, in response to technological change, in particular the advent and uptake of AI and progress towards AGI²³. This key question is considered and analysed in a successor paper on: “Likely Impacts of AI / AGI on the Modern Academic Journal Publication System” which predicts and outlines likely imminent huge systemic change²⁴.

²¹ See Wikipedia: “Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society” at https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Philosophical_Transactions_of_the_Royal_Society

²² See e.g., Wikipedia: “Physics (Aristotle)” (2025) at [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Physics_\(Aristotle\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Physics_(Aristotle))

²³ See e.g. Macey-Dare, Rupert, How Soon is Now? Predicting the Expected Arrival Date of AGI- Artificial General Intelligence (June 30, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4496418>

²⁴ See: MACEY-DARE, R. (2025). Likely Impacts of AI / AGI on the Modern Academic Journal Publication System. Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17599111>

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